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EPIGRAPHISCHE MITTEILUNGEN AUS ANTALYA VIII

FOUR EPIGRAMS FROM THE PERIPHERY OF NICAIA*

(Tafel 24)

The epigrams treated below were copied in 1982 by Sencer Şahin during his epigraphic survey in and around Nicaia. They were found in Beyyayla and İğdir Yaylası, two little villages in the middle of the Sangarios basin, some 15 km south-east of the town Yenipazar and 40 km north-east of Eskişehir/Dorylaion. The region belonged to Nicaia, which had a widespread territory (S. Şahin, *I. v. Nikaia I*, IX; Chr. Marek, *EA* 28, 1997, 81). The characteristic settlements there are villages and hamlets rather than towns. Many votive and funeral inscriptions (Şahin, *I. v. Nikaia II*, no. 1105; 1128, 1162; 1288; 1289; 1292; 1293; Merkelbach-Şahin; *EA* 1, 1983, 57; others will be published by M. Adak, *I. v. Nikaia III*) reveal the wealth of the population in the Roman Imperial Period.

The four inscriptions below have meanwhile also been published by R. Merkelbach – J. Stau-ber, *Steinepigramme aus dem griechischen Osten 2: Die Nordküste Kleinasiens* (München/Leipzig 2001), no.s 09/05/36, 09/05/37, 09/05/38, 09/05/32 respectively.

1. Epigram for Marcianus

The rectangular limestone stele, on top of which is a low basis surrounded by four acroteria on each corner of the moulding of the cornice, is built into a wall enclosing a mosque in Beyyayla.
H.: 1.65 m.; W.: 0.48 m.; D.: 0.42 m.; L.: 0.025–0.035 m.

* We are thankful to Mr. S. Şahin for his kind permission to publish these four epigrams and for his encouraging support during our study on them.

	τὸν κλυτὸν ἐν γῆι μέση γεω- πόνον ἄνδρα σεμνὸν ἢ ξενίῃ πάτρῃ μερόπων Ταταυέ- 04 α καλύπτει Μαρκιανὸν πο- λλοῖσι φίλον καὶ τεῖμιον ἄ- νδράσι πᾶσιν ἐργοπόνον φιλάδελφον φιλαλήθε- 08 α καὶ φιλόθρεπτον ὃν στεν- αχί σύλλεκτρος Χαρίτιν, ἢ γαμέτην προλιπούσα καὶ γλυ- κεροὶ παῖδες πατέρα τὸν ἐ- 12 πάξιον ἠδὲ πορίστην ἼΗ- δυλίῳ Μάρκος Μαρκιαν- ὸς Χρησσίῳ οἱ φιλοπατρ- εῖς ὅσα πρέπει μνήσ γενέ- 16 τη τὸδε σῆμα καμόντι	The hospitable fatherland of the mortals, Tatauea, embraces the, in the midland renowned, tiller of the soil, Marcianus; and Charition, his wife, groans for his brother – loving, truth-loving, slave-loving husband who was loved by most of the people and provided service to everybody, since he died untimely. Hedylion, Marcus, Marcianus and Chression, his dear children loving their respected and procuring father (erected) this monument so that only such things may suit the memory of such a diligent man
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Probably late 2nd century AD.

L.3/4 κατὰ γῆα proposed by Merkelbach – Stauber, *Steinepigramme* II, 188 seems less possible, since the reading Ταταυέα in the squeeze is sure.

The toponym of Tatauea (Ταταυέα) may either signify the same place called Tataion (Τάταιον), which is also known as Tatauion (Ταταούιον) located between Gölpazarı and Arıcaklar, comp. Şahin, I. v. Nikaia II,1, p. 59; Zgusta, *Ortsnamen* 604, or the present site near Beyyayla. On the other hand, Tatauea may, though less likely, be the ethnicon of Marcianus in the accusative form of Tataueus (Ταταυεύς). Be this as it may, it is more reasonable to admit Ταταυέα owing to the necessity of a toponym after the expression of ἢ ξενίῃ πάτρῃ.

L. 8 στοναχῖ = στοναχεῖ

L. 9 Χαρίτιν = Χαρίτιον, comp. SEG XXVIII 1978 no. 1154 (Χαρίτιν ἢ προίκος [τῆ] ἃ] πελευθέρῃ Ευτυχ[ίῃ]). For the syncope of the vowel "o" in this way in the inscriptions of the Roman Period, see Cl. Brixhe, *Essai sur le grec anatolien au début de notre ère*, Nancy² 1987, p. 49.

L. 15 μνής = μνήμης χάριν, comp. L. Robert, *Hellenica* XIII (1965), p. 71; S. Şahin, *Ein Kindersarkophag aus Umurbey im Museum von İzmit*, in: EA 3 (1984), p. 108.

2. Epigram for Hedylion

A limestone stele very similar to the one above no. 1 is built into a garden wall in Beyyayla. Between the front acroteria there is a patera on the basis, a stylus-case and a manuscript roll below the inscription.

H.: 1.38 m.; W.: 0.46 m.; D.: 0.42 m.; L.: 0.025–0.030 m.

τὸν πᾶσιν μερόπεσσι φίλ-
 ὄν καὶ τίμιον ἄνδρα Ἴδουλι-
 ὄνα σοφὸν, φθίμενον νέον [ὦ]
 04 παροδεῖτα· Χαρίτιν ἢ μήτη[ρ]
 πινυτὴ μύρατο ἀχθομένη,
 κλειτοὶ ἀδελφοὶ Μάρκ-
 08 ος, Μαρκιανὸς, Χρηστός τε
 Δόμνα γυνὴ σαόφρων καὶ
 γνήσια τέκνα τοκῆα Μαρ-
 κιάνη, Μαρκιανὸς, Ἴδου-
 λος, Εὐσέβιος τε Χαρίτ-
 12 ιν ἢ θυγάτηρ, ἐπ[ι]μύζιον, ἣν κατέ-
 λιπεν, οἱ καὶ τὴν στήλην
 στήσαν ἐς ἔσθε κλέος.

O, passer-by!
 salute Marcianus the learned man
 who was loved and highly esteemed
 by all the mortals and who died
 very young. Charition, his mother,
 was weighed down with grief
 and shed tears after him, and the
 renowned brothers Marcus, Marcianus
 and Chrestos, and Domna, his prudent
 wife, and the legitimate children
 Marciana, Marcianus, Hedylos, Eusebios
 and his daughter Charition who was
 left behind as a babe in arms,
 erected this stele to glorify him.

Probably early 3rd century A.D.

Domna, wife of Marcianus, seems to have been named after Septimius Severus' wife. The Severian period is also confirmed by the form of the letters. Moreover the Latin names appearing together with the Greek ones suggest that this local family had obtained Roman citizenship before the Constitutio Antoniniana.

L. 14 ἐς ἔσθε = εἰς ἔσθαι

It is deducible from the pedigree above that Chression, whose name also appears in the first epigram, had already died when the second inscription was engraved. Meanwhile a son named Chrestos joined the family after the death of Marcianus, the father. Charition must have been pregnant when her husband died.

3. Epigram for Neicys

This limestone stele is almost identical in shape to the second one above. No manuscript roll but a stylus-case is found below the inscription. The stone is used as one of the corner stones of a modern building in İğdir Yaylası.

H.: 1.85 m.; W.: 0.52 m.; D.: 0.29-0.35 m.; L.: 0.025-0.045 m.

	Νεΐκυς Ἀγαθειόνο- ς πολυήρατος ᾧδ- ε τέθαπται ὄρφαν-	Neicys, son of Agatheion, that very lovely man is buried here.
04	ἅ καὶ γαμετὴν προλιπ- ὼν ταχέως ὁ πρόμοι- ρος. ἐκτέρισεν μήτηρ δ-	He passed away untimely, leaving his wife behind instantly and his children as orphans.
08	ε Πώλλα καὶ Πωλλί- ων φιλάδελφος ἴν' ὁ- ψιγόνους κλεός εἶη	Polla, his mother, and Pollion the brother-loving, paid honors here for the blessed, in order to be a glory to the late-born generations.

3rd century A.D.

4. Epigram for Nicon

A large white marble stele similar in shape to no. 1 above is used as a corner stone of a modern building in İğdir Yaylası. There is a stylus-case below the inscription.

H.: 1.68 m.; W.: 0.45-0.57 m.; D.: 0.45-0.49 m.; L.: 0.025-0.030 m.

	Πατρὸς μὲν Νίκωνος ἐγὼ θάνον, ᾧ Γανυμή- δης μητέρα τε προλιπὼν	Alas, I, my father Nicon's son, Ganymedes, died leaving my mother Eia behind
04	Ἴαν ἐν πενθεῖ λυγρῷ σῆμα δέ μοι τόδ' ἔθοντο ἐπὶ χθονὶ πέδες ἀγαυοὶ Νει- κήτης καὶ Εὐτυχίδης	in a mournful sorrow. My noble children Neicetes and Eutyichides, together with Asclepiodotos
08	σὺν Ἀσκληπιοδότῳ φι- λάδελφοι κὲ Εἶα γαμη- τῇ δάκρουσι μυρομένη κὲ Ἀσκληῆς φιλάδελφ-	and my wife Eia who shed tears erected this stele on earth for me and Ascles made the
12	ος τύμβον ἐπεκτέρι- σεν.	tomb.

3rd centry A.D.

L. 4 Ἴαν = Εἶαν

L. 5 ἔθοντο = ἔθεντο

L. 6 πέδες = παῖδες

The family relationship in the epigram cannot be clarified. However, Eutyichides, Neicetes and Asclepiodotos seem to be the sons of Ganymedes. His mother and wife both bore the same name, Eia, but Ia is specifically used only for the mother in order to identify her. In that case the pedigree should be as follows:

Akdeniz Üniversitesi/Antalya
Akdeniz Üniversitesi/Antalya

Burak Takmer
Nihal Tüner

ÖZET

ANTALYA'DAN EPIGRAFI HABERLERİ VIII: Nikaia Çevresinden 4 Epigram

Burada tanıtılan dört epigram, Sencer Şahin tarafından Nikaia teritoryumunda yürütülen epigrafi araştırmalarında 1982 yılında bulunarak kopyalanmıştır. İ. S. II. yüzyıl sonu III. yüzyıl başına tarihlenen epigramların düzenli bir vezni yoktur.

1. Marcianus'un Mezar Epigramı:

Ölümlülerin misafirperver vatanı Tatauia saklıyor bağrında (memleketin) iç kısımlarında nam salmış, toprak emekçisi Marcianus'u. Chariti(o)n, çok kimsenin sevdiği ve saydığı, tüm insanların hizmetindeki, kardeşsever, gerçeksever ve beslemesever kocasına, onu vakitsiz kaybettiği için ahüzar eder. Pek sevimli, çocukları Hedylion, Marcus, Marcianus ve Chression; babasever kişiler olarak, çalışkan bir insanın anısına böyle şeyler yakıştır diye (diktiler bu anıtı)

2. Hedylion'un Mezar Epigramı:

Ey, yolcu ! Tüm ölümlüler içinde dost ve saygın insan, genç yaşta ölen, bilge Hedylion'u (selamla). Acılar içinde yas tutan anne Chariti(o)n gözyaşı döker. Soylu kardeşleri Marcus, Marcianus ve Khrestos, erdemli eşi Domna ve de meşru çocukları Marciana, Marcianus, Hedylos, Eusebios ve geride bıraktığı emzikteki kızı Chariti(o)n bu steli ün olsun diye diktiler.

3. Neikys'in Mezar Epigramı:

Agateion oğlu Neikys, O, çok yönlü insan burada gömülü; Yetim bırakıp çocuklarını ve çarçabuk terkedip eşini vakitsiz gitti. Annesi Polla ve kardeşsever Pollion gelecek kuşaklara ün olsun diye rahmetliyi buraya defnetti.

4. Nikon'un Mezar Epigramı:

Babam Nikon'un oğlu, ben Ganymedes annem Eia'yı tarifsiz bir keder içinde bırakarak öldüm, ah !... Neicetes ve Euthychides, Asklepiodotos ve göz yaşlarına boğulan karım Eia ile birlikte bu mezarı toprak üstüne benim için diktiler. Kardeşsever Askles ise mezarın üzerini örttü.

No. 2

No. 3

No. 4

Four Epigrams from the Periphery of Nicaia; B. Takmer – N. Tüner, pp. 179–183